

The impact of motivation on learner retention

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It is well established that motivation significantly influences how learners acquire and apply new skills. Motivational processes, including those grounded in Self-Determination Theory, can enhance the cultural identity of low-performing students. This is particularly relevant given that learning is not culturally neutral. This literature review summarises key findings on motivation in relation to culturally appropriate practices and provides suggestions for future research. Key findings indicate that most intervention studies emphasise the importance of addressing cultural bias and tailoring interventions to meet individual student needs. Furthermore, culturally responsive teacher training, conducted both individually and in groups, is identified as essential. The studies reviewed were primarily conducted in school settings in the US and Europe and were predominantly qualitative. Consequently, current research may lack rigour and generalisability due to its focus on Western samples. Future studies could address this limitation by incorporating data from non-Western cultures and other settings, such as universities, to enhance the broader applicability of findings. Additionally, increasing the use of quantitative measures could improve the rigour of research. Employing mixed-methods approaches would also be beneficial, enabling the triangulation of data to evaluate both intervention outcomes (using quantitative methods to explore what happens) and processes (using qualitative methods to examine how and why outcomes are achieved).

Keywords: cultural identity; motivation; self-determination theory; students; teacher training

Humans tend to be proactive and want to work towards improving themselves (Reeve, 2012). According to Wlodkowski and Ginsberg (1995), to support students who are thought of as low performing, it is important for tutors to think about ways of increasing student intrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation is long lasting and the reasons behind this type of motivation are related to how the student views themselves and their inner goals, not affected by outside sources such as fear of punishment (Reeve, 2012).

According to Self-Motivation theory (SDT; Deci & Ryan, 2000) everyone has innate motivational resources (basic psychological needs). Autonomy, competence and relatedness are the basic psychological needs – autonomy is when one has control of their decisions; competence is when someone can complete tasks; relatedness is connecting with others (Deci & Ryan, 1985). When the needs are satisfied, students are more likely to have intrinsic motivation towards behaviour. On the other hand, if the needs are frustrated, this leads to amotivation or extrinsic motivation. For the needs to be satisfied, an autonomy supportive environment should be created the lecturer. Thus, the focus of the SDT model of teaching is creating opportunities for people to help themselves to achieve in the class and be motivated for reasons important to their sense of self.

Numerous studies have shown that when students are intrinsically motivated due to their basic needs being satisfied, their achievement, intentions to pursue further education and careers in a particular domain, and satisfaction is also improved (Boiché et al., 2008; Lavigne et al., 2007; Standage et al., 2006; Sun et al., 2017;).

Motivational framework for culturally responsive teaching

It has been shown that people tend to have the same trends in terms of Self-Determination Theory across a range of cultures, such as Bulgaria, Italy, America, Brazil, and Canada (Chirkov et al., 2005; Deci et al., 2001; Ginevra et al., 2013; Nalipay et al., 2020). However, the link between culture and learning motivation cannot be denied, as needs satisfaction (based on an autonomy-supportive environment) is likely to lead to stronger wellbeing levels and higher cultural identity (Chirkov et al., 2005). This could be because when someone has intrinsic motivation towards learning, they are in an environment that promotes relatedness (connecting with others), which can make people feel happier and more accepted, and like they belong in terms of their culture.

According to Martorana (2022) culture can also affect motivation. This is the case because the fact that students are not the same as each other culturally can be used in class (for instance by asking students to share experiences of learning in their country of origin), which may lead to higher levels of inclusion. When students are included, they feel respected and connected to others, which are similar aspects to relatedness (Martorana, 2022). Therefore, if tutors are aware and inclusive when teaching culturally different students (culturally responsive), this could lead to higher inclusion and relatedness, satisfying one of the basic psychological needs and working towards creating an environment which fosters intrinsic motivation. Additionally, culturally responsive teaching (Ladson-Billings, 1995) leads to increases in autonomy (as students feel they have more choice due to tutors being aware of their cultural needs and traditions) and competence (as inclusive assessments can be created if tutors know about their students' culture). Therefore, culturally responsive teaching can be used to support all three basic psychological needs (Vansteenkiste et al., 2020).

Wlodkowski and Ginsberg (1995) proposed a framework related to this, called the Motivation framework for Culturally Responsive Teaching. The key idea of the framework is that learning situations are never culturally neutral, so it is important to create conditions to satisfy the basic psychological needs in a culturally responsive manner. The four motivational conditions that teachers should create are establishing inclusion, developing a positive attitude, enhancing meaning and engendering competence. Establishing inclusion is when teachers ensure that the learning environment fosters connectedness and respect. Developing a positive attitude is when learning is made to be relevant to student interests and promotes choice. Enhancing meaning is when challenges learning moments include different perspectives. Engendering competence is about helping students

achieve their goals in a way that is relevant and authentic to the student identities. The four conditions work together over time to create intrinsic motivation for learning (Relojo et al., 2016).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Surveys have been produced to measure culturally responsive teaching (CRT) skills, knowledge, views on the importance of CRT, and self-efficacy (Abacioglu et al., 2020; Callaway, 2017; Chu & Garcia, 2014; Comstock et al., 2023; Cruz et al., 2020; Fiedler et al., 2008; Fitchett et al., 2012; Frye et al., 2010; Heitner & Jennings, 2016; Hsiao, 2015; Larson et al., 2018; Oyerinde, 2008; Rhodes, 2013a, 2013b, 2017; Siwatu, 2007)

The surveys tend to be more geared towards school level teaching, whereas only a few research works focus on adult learner teaching (Heitner & Jennings, 2016; Rhodes, 2013a, 2013b, 2017). The studies based on the work of teachers of adult students used Culturally Responsive Teaching Survey (CRTS) and Culturally Responsive Teaching Knowledge and Practice Survey (CRTKPS). CRTS (Rhodes, 2013a, 2013b, 2017) is directly based on the motivational framework for CRT (Wlodkowski & Ginsberg &, 1995), whereas CRTKPS (Heitner & Jennings, 2016) is based on a review of literature about CRT.

CRTS is shorter (17 items) than the CRTKPS (73 items). Also, the CRTKPS has different sections (knowledge, value and importance of CRT, use of skills, meeting needs of different communities, abilities), with one of the sections having a much larger number of questions than others. CRTS is focused on the frequency of lecturer use of cultural practices.

Heitner and Jennings (2016) CRTKPS study participants were tutors working at a higher education faculty and teaching undergraduates and graduates ($n = 39$) online and participants for the Rhodes (2017) CRTS study were adult education ESOL teachers ($n = 134$) working face to face. Both studies were conducted in US.

In terms of reliability, CRTS was shown to have high level of internal reliability at Cronbach's alpha of .834. The CRTKPS overall Cronbach's alpha was .95, also indicative of very high internal reliability.

Construct validity of CRTS was examined via comparison with a different survey, the Multicultural Teaching Competencies Scale (MTCS). This approach is known as convergent validity (a part of construct validity). It was shown that there were significant correlations between the two surveys, which suggest that CRTS has convergent validity. The Campbell-Fiske multitrait-multimethod matrix was used to show that CRTKPS has construct validity.

Content validity of CRTS was assessed via using two expert panels. The first panel included staff with a lot of ESOL teaching experiences looked for clarity and relevance to second language teaching theory. The second panel for made up of experts in culturally responsive teaching who analysed the items for relevance to adult learning and CRT. CRTS was also developed using cognitive interviews and a pilot study of 100 adult ESOL teachers (resulting Cronbach's alpha was .752). The CRTKPS instrument content validity also included a panel (10 faculty and former students from minority and international backgrounds) who analysed the items in terms of clarity and evidence. Additionally, CRTKPS development included four interviews after the surveys were completed. The interviews also showed face validity.

The CRTS study showed that most frequently used practices were "examine class materials for appropriate images and themes" and "use mixed-language and mixed-cultural pairings in group work". The least frequently used practices were "include lessons about anti-immigrant discrimination or bias" and "students work independently, selecting their own learning activities". Additionally, the highest percentage of staff stated that they never "encourage students to use their native language with their children".

The results of CRTKPS were that more staff agreed with the high value of CRT but did not perceive themselves to have good knowledge of CRT. However, participants felt they have higher knowledge of CRT than about meeting the needs of different communities.

CRTS is a shorter measure focused on how often staff apply certain practices related to CRT. On the other hand, CRTKPS was focused on practice and knowledge and values but had too many items. Also, CRTS sample was larger, making the study more generalisable. Additionally, CRTS may be preferable for use in the present study as it is directly based on theory of motivation and CRT. Therefore, CRTS should be used in the future studies as opposed to CRT.

The research gap to be addressed in future research is about exploring whether CRTS can be used in different cultures (such as UK). The terminology would have to be defined clearly, as in the UK; the term “acculturation” is not widely used within university or school settings.

Additionally, CRTS results can be used to generate reflections from staff (teachers or lecturers). It may also be useful to apply the survey in slightly different settings to that of Rhodes (2013a, 2013b, 2017) to test the survey validity across various settings (such as university or college). One example could be using the survey with lecturer participants where students taught at the institution in question are from mature and widening participation backgrounds, as well as often belonging to a different culture to the lecturer.

Review of interventions

Theoretical underpinnings are important to help to understand which elements of culturally responsive practice should be used within surveys. The next step is to gain understanding of how theory has been used within interventions on the culturally responsive practices and how effective the interventions are.

A review by Bottiani et al. (2017) summarised the results of 10 studies (8 of which were qualitative) about culturally responsive teaching interventions. It was shown that most interventions included culturally responsive practice training. The studies were done in US, which limits their generalisability to other populations. Additionally, the studies were all based in schools.

It is worth noting that the operationalisation of culturally responsive practices was highly varied. For instance, it was operationalised as a way of students helping to enhance curriculum with their cultural knowledge, interactions between parents and teachers and the influence of culture on teaching decisions. Overall, the study design was not evidence-based but interesting conclusions were shown, nonetheless. For examples, there was improvement in teacher knowledge, skills and using CRP, as well as possible improvement in student outcomes. After the interventions, some teachers found it challenging to apply their new knowledge. It seems that the field of CRP interventions is currently in the early stages and more rigorous research is needed to ascertain the full efficacy of interventions on the topic.

Another review was about teacher training in preparation and professional development programmes (Romijn et al., 2021). The outcomes of 45 studies were included, with a focus on teachers working with students who ranged between toddlers and high school students as well as teachers still in teacher training. However, only a small amount of the papers focused on culturally responsive teaching, while most papers were on cultural diversity. However, 96% of the papers focused on reflection in the trainings on different aspects related to cultural competency, which is also a large part of culturally responsive practice.

Similar findings were shown to that of Bottiani et al., (2017) in that teacher often found it difficult to apply new knowledge in their practice. In one study (Daniel & Pray, 2017), it was found that application of new skills in class increased following one to one coaching, with teachers then being able to incorporate the children’s first language more in the classroom. The review highlights the

importance of supporting teachers to apply their knowledge in practice and that reflection on cultural biases should be encouraged.

Additionally, the review suggests that context of the educational establishment has a large effect on whether the new strategies and skills of culturally responsive practices will be implemented effectively or not. Therefore, the interventions should be tailored in terms of providing coaching specific to individual teachers as well as being aware of the situations within the organisation where the intervention is taking place. Once again, like the review of Bottiani et al. (2017), this review shows that the research on interventions is limited and not overly rigorous. This suggests that the interventions on culturally responsive practices are still being developed and have not yet become commonly available. Also, research seems to focus on school-aged children, ignoring establishments with mature students who experience different issues to younger groups.

A review of culturally responsive teaching of mathematics (Abdulrahim & Orosco, 2020) may also provide ideas about how interventions on culturally responsive teaching can be conducted, despite its specific mathematical teaching focus. This review includes 35 studies conducted in schools in the US. Most studies ($n = 26$) were qualitative, which means that results of the review are not highly rigorous. The key findings were that using culturally responsive curriculums and interaction styles helped the students to feel more empowered and results in better grades. Finally, the review supports the work of previous researchers in showing that teachers should reflect on culture to be critical and aware of issues surrounding the lack of equity and acceptance of diversity to implement change and engage in culturally responsive teaching practices. The critical reflection skills can then be passed on to the students to enhance their learning further.

As well as focusing on interventions to improve the culturally responsive practices within the classroom, it is possible to also include culturally responsive assessments, as per the topic of the review of Nortvedt et al. (2020). The 103 papers of the review are focused on the experiences of assessments of migrant school students in Europe. Assessments can be considered culturally responsive if they are focused on how students from different cultures communicate, according to Hood (1998). The findings of 103 papers and book chapters were that culturally responsive assessment should be performance-based (encouraging students to use new skills), include students assessing themselves and giving feedback to peers, include creative thinking and dynamic (tailored to the students' language skills and processing skills). It appears that to ensure fair and culturally responsive assessments takes place, teachers need to learn how students from different cultures communicate, what language issues students have and how students could use their own language in assessment. Another aspect that appears vital to encouraging culturally responsive assessment approaches is focus on individual student needs.

CONCLUSION

Most research on interventions for culturally responsive practice improvement in education was conducted in school settings, within US or Europe, which limits the generalisability of the knowledge. Many of the research studies also appear to be of a low standard in terms of research rigour, with little quantitative research conducted at this stage. However, some interesting findings were obtained from the interventions. It appears that reflection on cultural bias is an important aspect of encouraging teachers to use culturally responsive practice. Additionally, the research studies results suggest that it is important to tailor the interventions to each student while also being aware of the context within the school environment. Finally, whilst most interventions used group staff training as a way of improving knowledge, implementation of the use of culturally responsive teaching approaches within the classroom was largely enhanced through individual coaching of teachers. The key lessons from the intervention research should be applied to creating interventions not just within the school settings but expanded further to university and college settings.

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